

1
2
3
4
5
6
7
8
9
10
11
12
13
14
15
16
17
18
19
20
21
22
23
24
25
26
27
28

Therapeutic targeting in colorectal cancer for the treatment of liver metastasis: SGK3.

Shahan K. Mamoor, B.S., M.S., Ph.D cand.¹
¹shahanmamoor@gmail.com
Chestnut Hill, MA USA 02467
East Islip, NY USA 11730

The liver is the most common site of metastasis in patients with colorectal cancer (1-5). We recently utilized whole transcriptome technologies to define the full complement of differentially expressed kinases and phosphatases in HER2+ breast cancer: in the primary tumor, and in metastasis to the CNS (6-8). Measuring total transcription with RNA-sequencing and microarray in metastasis and the cancer (primary tumor) from which they are derived enables rational design and development of novel chemotherapies with optimized therapeutic index (9). Here we utilize whole transcriptome technologies (10, 11) to measure total transcription in the liver metastases of humans with colorectal cancer. We describe a therapeutic target that is up-regulated and differentially expressed in liver metastasis in humans with colorectal cancer, *SGK3*, as a candidate therapeutic target for the medical management of liver metastasis in human colorectal cancer.

We utilize genomic and transcriptomic technologies to study the genomic sequences (DNA), the transcriptome (RNA), and epigenetic modification (eg., CpG-DNA) of humans with cancer. This includes the primary tumor, the source of the transformation - like mutant variants of p53 - subtypes of the primary tumor, including luminal, basal and HER2+ forms in breast cancer, and adeno and squamous forms of NSCLC in lung cancer, "regional" metastasis to the liver, metastasis to distant sites, including the colorectals, the liver and the brain, and the circulating tumor stem cell. Here we measure total transcription in metastasis to the liver to discover and describe a therapeutic target identified through rigorous study of the liver metastatic transcriptome in colorectal cancer: a therapeutic target that is up-regulated and metastasis-specific, providing ideal therapeutic index to minimize toxicity and maximize efficacy: SGK3.

Results

Figure 1: SGK3 is differentially expressed in liver metastasis in humans with colorectal cancer.

I. Liver metastasis and primary tumors from humans with colorectal cancer.

n=4 primary tumors from humans with colorectal cancer
n=3 liver metastases from humans with colorectal cancer

GeneID	<i>p</i> -value	lfcSE	stat	log2FC	baseMean	Gene	Rank	%DE
23678	3.00E-02	0.584	-2.1698866	-1.2668589	46.9	SGK3	2826/19486	85.5

Through quantitative comparison of total transcription in the primary tumors of the colorectum and in liver metastases of humans with colorectal cancer, we discovered differential expression of serum/glucocorticoid regulated kinase family member 3, encoded by SGK3 in metastasis to the liver in humans with colorectal cancer (**Chart 1**). The expression of SGK3 changed more than 85% of the human colorectal cancer (CRC) liver metastatic transcriptome when considering all transcripts whose expression was measured - in this case, 19,486 transcripts ("Rank"). Note the negative fold-change indicating increased quantity of SGK3 messenger RNA in CRC liver metastases, demonstrating up-regulation of SGK3 during disease progression in colorectal cancer.

II. Liver metastasis in patients with colorectal cancer.

n=10 primary tumors from humans with colorectal cancer
n=10 liver metastases from humans with colorectal cancer

GeneID	<i>p</i> -value	lfcSE	stat	log2FC	baseMean	Gene	Rank	%DE
23678	3.47E-02	0.361	-2.1119493	-0.76280065	38.87	SGK3	2379/15341	84.5

Through measurement of total transcription in the liver metastases of humans with colorectal cancer as compared to primary tumors of the colon and rectum, we validated differential expression of SGK3 in human colorectal cancer (**Chart 2**). The expression of SGK3 here changed more than nearly 85% of the liver metastatic transcriptome when considering all transcripts whose expression was measured - in this case, 15,341 transcripts ("Rank"). Note the negative fold-change indicating increased quantity of SGK3 messenger RNA in liver metastases, demonstrating up-regulation of SGK3 during disease progression and metastasis in humans with colorectal cancer.

1
2
3
4
5
6
7
8
9
10
11
12
13
14
15
16
17
18
19
20
21
22
23
24
25
26
27
28

Thus, differential and increased expression of SGK3 defines the liver metastatic transcriptome in human colorectal cancer.

Discussion

Adjunctive treatments in medical oncology limit the emergence of resistant tumor clones during treatment with a second agent (whether neoadjuvantive chemotherapy or a targeted therapy like trastuzumab). Inhibitors of SGK3, once evaluated for toxicity and safety, can immediately be tested for efficacy in patients with liver metastasis who have failed previous treatment, with the goal of identifying the most effective inhibitors of liver metastasis in humans with colorectal cancer. A multi-kinase approach delivered in conjunction with chemotherapies that target dNTP synthesis, replication of the daughter strand and activity at the spindle at anaphase, and target *CDKN* inactivation and ATP-binding cassette pump expression in resistant cases, is most likely to be most effective in limiting tumor clone resistance (12).

References

1. Tsilimigras, D.I., Brodt, P., Clavien, P.A., Muschel, R.J., D'Angelica, M.I., Endo, I., Parks, R.W., Doyle, M., de Santibañes, E. and Pawlik, T.M., 2021. Liver metastases. *Nature reviews Disease primers*, 7(1), p.27.
2. Siriwardena, A.K., Mason, J.M., Mullamitha, S., Hancock, H.C. and Jegatheeswaran, S., 2014. Management of colorectal cancer presenting with synchronous liver metastases. *Nature reviews Clinical oncology*, 11(8), pp.446-459.
3. Dueland, S., Yaqub, S., Syversveen, T., Carling, U., Hagness, M., Brudvik, K.W. and Line, P.D., 2021. Survival outcomes after portal vein embolization and liver resection compared with liver transplant for patients with extensive colorectal cancer liver metastases. *JAMA surgery*, 156(6), pp.550-557.
4. Dueland, S., Smedman, T.M., Syversveen, T., Grut, H., Hagness, M. and Line, P.D., 2023. Long-term survival, prognostic factors, and selection of patients with colorectal cancer for liver transplant: a nonrandomized controlled trial. *JAMA surgery*, 158(9), pp.e232932-e232932.
5. Karanicolas, P.J., Jarnagin, W.R., Gonen, M., Tuorto, S., Allen, P.J., DeMatteo, R.P., D'Angelica, M.I. and Fong, Y., 2013. Long-term outcomes following tumor ablation for treatment of bilateral colorectal liver metastases. *JAMA surgery*, 148(7), pp.597-601.
6. Mamoor, Shahan. 2024. Increased rate of CNS metastasis in patients with HER2+ breast cancer is a result of the intrinsic gene expression program of HER2+ subtype breast cancers, not a consequence of use of the HER2+-targeted drug trastuzumab.
7. Mamoor, Shahan. 2024. Kinase targeting in HER2+ breast cancer to prevent and treat CNS disease: CDK8.
8. Mamoor, Shahan. 2024. Catalytic site targeting in HER2+ breast cancer for the treatment of CNS metastasis: PPP1R3D.
9. Muller, P.Y. and Milton, M.N., 2012. The determination and interpretation of the therapeutic index in drug development. *Nature reviews Drug discovery*, 11(10), pp.751-761.
10. GSE179979: The Sixth Affiliated Hospital of Sun Yat-sen University. Department of Colorectal Surgery. Guangzhou, China.
11. GSE213402: Rodger, E.J., Gimenez, G., Ajithkumar, P., Stockwell, P.A., Almomani, S., Bowden, S.A., Leichter, A.L., Ahn, A., Pattison, S., McCall, J.L. and Schmeier, S., 2023. An epigenetic signature of advanced colorectal cancer metastasis. *IScience*, 26(6).
12. Mamoor, Shahan. 2024. Therapeutic targeting of catalytically available solid tumor vulnerabilities in human cancer.

1
2
3
4
5
6
7
8
9
10
11
12
13
14
15
16
17
18
19
20
21
22
23
24
25
26
27
28

Methods

We utilized GSE213402 and GSE179979 for this tumor transcriptome study, measuring whole transcription in metastasis to the liver and in primary tumors from humans with colorectal cancer using RNA-sequencing data (public and published) and R-based computational methods.